

LINGUISTIC PECULIARITIES OF SYNTACTICAL STYLISTIC DEVICES

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ABSTRACT

The main aim of this article is to highlight the importance of syntactical stylistic devices to be able to paraphrase and express thoughts impressively in speaking and writing. Syntactical stylistic devices are based on the syntactical arrangement of the elements of a sentences or a paragraph. Besides there is a comparatively large group of syntactical stylistic devices in which the stylistic effect is achieved not only through a peculiar syntactical structure of the utterance, but also through the employment of the semantical side of its elements. They include inversion, parallelism, climax, repetition, asyndeton, rhetorical question, and question in narrative.

On May 6, 2021, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev chaired a meeting on measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages. Uzbekistan's policy of openness, active entry into the global market, expansion of international cooperation in all areas increase the need for studying foreign languages.

The task has been set to introduce salary increments for teachers who have received an international certificate with an initial and secondary level – in the amount of 40 percent, and for those who have achieved a high level – in the amount of 50 percent. [1]

Considering that there are numerous opportunities for people who have great knowledge and especially language certificates in Uzbekistan, people really try to comprehend the language. Not only knowing how to make simple sentences, but only being informed about different stylistic devices helps people to speak and write more impressively. Especially people need to be aware of the importance of such stylistic devices as repetition, asyndeton, parallelism, ellipsis, inversion in order to be able to write literary texts and poems effectively. This article aims to improve people's ability to understand and use abovementioned stylistic devices. Related to the topic, we refer to the following works in which researchers analyzed syntactical stylistic devices from various sides.

Stylistic devices (abbreviated as "SD") are intentional combinations of expressive and figurative language elements at many levels (phonetic, graphic, grammatical, lexical, and textual) with

dynamically changing functions, such as amplification, displacement, or generalization [2]. With the help of them, deep meanings of authors' thoughts can be expressed without difficulty.

English's syntactic SDs can be split into three categories:

1. Syntactic SDs rely on the purposeful deletion of some sentence components to reduce the sentence model. Aposiopesis, asyndeton, and ellipsis are all members of this category.
2. Syntactic SDs, which extend the sentence model by include new features or by purposeful repetition. Repetition, enumeration, chiasmus, and polysyndeton all belong to this group.
3. Syntactic SDs rely on purposeful sentence fragmentation or a disruption in the grammatical phrase's set word order. This category includes rhetorical devices such as inversion, detachment, parallel construction, and rhetorical query [3].

SDs of expressive means are those that are syntactic. That together make a full syntactic framework, which is regarded as their most typical characteristic. One of the Syntactic SDs is the techniques for generating using syntactic-intonation expressiveness in literature and the arts fulfill a particular methodological task. Specific syntactic turnovers are known as syntactic SDs. That aid in enhancing the emotional impact of speech, this involves repetition, parallelism, and its kinds, ellipses, antithesis, stylistic inversion, and gradation. Repetition is one of the most widely utilized syntactic SDs in literary language. A SD called repetition is most frequently employed to convey excitement. Speech that is emotionally charged tends to be brief, logical, and repetitive of the same ideas. With the goal of discovering the solution, numerous conversations about repetition are conducted [4]. As an example, we can see repetition in Ann Patchett's work: "So I said yes to Thomas Clinton and later thought that I had said yes to God and later still realized I had said yes only to Thomas Clinton". [5]

Syntactical stylistic devices are frequently used not only in literary texts, but also in poetry. Poets can convey their inner thoughts and feelings effectively with such devices, not just simple words.

An elliptical sentence is such a syntactic structure in which there is no subject, or predicate, or both. The main parts of elliptical sentences are omitted by the speaker intentionally in cases when they are semantically redundant. In poetry, the omission of words whose absence does not impede the reader's ability to understand the expression. For example, Shakespeare makes frequent use of the phrase "I will away" in his plays, with the missing verb understood to be "go." T.S. Eliot employs ellipsis in the following passage from "Preludes". [6]

You curled the papers from your hair,

Or clasped the yellow soles of

In the palms of both soiled hands.

The possessive "your" is left out in the second and third lines, but it can be assumed that the woman addressed by the speaker is clasping the soles of her own feet with her own hands. [7]

Ellipsis saves the speaker from needless effort, spares his time, reduces redundancy of speech. Elliptical structures may also reveal such speakers' emotions as excitement, impatience, delight, etc. As a stylistic device, ellipsis is an effective means of protagonists' portrayal. [8]

Stylistic repetition of language units in speech (separate words, word-combinations or sentences) is one of the most frequent and potent stylistic devices. Repetition is when words or phrases are repeated in a literary work. Repetition is often used in poetry or song, and it is used to create rhythm and bring attention to an idea. Repetition is also often used in speech, as a rhetorical device to bring attention to an idea. For example:

The woods are lovely dark and deep

But I have promises to keep

And miles to go before I sleep,

And miles to go before I sleep.

These are very famous lines from “Stopping by the woods in the snowy evening” of Frost. Here the person is standing in the snowy evening along with his horse. He is pondering at the beauty of surrounding when his horse alarmed him. He is ready to go back because he has to perform worldly duties and tasks. Here through repetition, the poet wants to express his devotion towards his responsibilities and also gives rhythm to the lines. [9]

Inversion is the syntactic phenomenon of intentional changing word order of the initial sentence model:

Sometime too hot the eye of heaven shines,

And often is his gold complexion dimmed,

And every fair from fair sometime declines,

By chance, or nature's changing course untrimmed:

So long as men can breathe, or eyes can see,

So long lives this, and this gives life to thee.

William Shakespeare in “Sonnet 18” used many examples of inversion in his plays and poetry, both anastrophe and anaclysis.

It can be seen that stylistic devices are broadly used not only in English literature, but also in other languages. Author in any literary work expresses some special ideas with their viewpoint and thoughts. They are stylistic units used to achieve emotional impact. One of the main goal is to use not only lexical opportunities of the language, but also syntactic ones. As an example we can see “The wind old man and his windy, rainy way” by Sh.Seytov:

Houses - reinforced concrete – in its background,

Pains - reinforced concrete – in its background,

Streams - reinforced concrete – in its background,

The brave – marble, concrete – in its background!

In this poem, the old man who sees and lives in the difficult period of the Soviet Union in the previous century, the Second World War tries to keep his family after the war is told about. The poet used the phrase “temir beton” – “reinforced concrete” to express the feelings and thoughts. This phrase is actually a metaphor. Iron and concrete can express the hardness of any object. With this stylistic device the poet tried to express the pains and sadness of the character during that period, lack of democracy, lack of will in both moral and physical society.

In these lines, metaphor is used among figurative devices. But there are also other poetic elements which give expressive meaning. They are stylistic devices. Repetition, parallelism, gradation and inversion are used in the abovementioned lines. In every line of the poem there is given a phrase “reinforced concrete – in its background”. Houses, pains, streams are used in parallel sides, which is parallelism.

With gradation, the ideas and thoughts get stronger and stronger. As the social and political viewpoints of the lyrical character strengthen, the idea about the person is given in the fourth line: “reinforced concrete” is exchanged with “marble concrete”. “Marble concrete” is the symbol of the monument which was built for the died in the second World War. The poet gradually makes the feelings stronger with the help of gradation and expresses the guilty of the cruel war. Thus, to the nature of lyrical expressions, work related to the psychological state of the hero, the poetic-syntax constructions are the only forms of the speech structure.

The research shows that the importance of stylistic device can be shown not only in literal language but also the spoken language to show how rich somebody’s vocabulary basement. Being aware of stylistic devices leads you get higher achievements in speaking and writing an essay as the most difficult ones are considered as “Speaking”, and “Writing”. Comprehension of SD can lead the student to broaden his or her ideas so that while teaching the students above mentioned skills it should be taught more. It can be said that being aware of syntactical stylistic devices and what meanings they give and how to use them helps not only readers, but also speakers and writers. Especially in our country, where English is being given more and more attention by the government, the importance of syntactical stylistic devices cannot be denied.

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